

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF
UNIDIRECTIONALLY REINFORCED PLASTICS UNDER
COMPRESSION

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INTRODUCTION

Compression failure is one of the least understood aspects of fibre reinforced composites failure in general. The catch is that there is a range of compression failure mechanisms: the microbuckling of fibers, ply separation delamination, squashing of specimen ends and plane shear at 45° to the loading axis.

The present paper deals with the compression failure specifics of glass and organic fibre reinforced plastics. Matrices were prepared out of various epoxide combinations. Ring specimens 150 mm in diameter were obtained by wet winding on the mandrel. Unidirectional cylindrical rod specimens 9 mm in diameter were prepared by drawing a preimpregnated yarn thro-

ugh a steel pipe with appropriate inner diameter. To produce flat specimens with the 2 by 10 mm cross-section, filaments were wet-wound on the flat mandrel and then subjected to post-pressing under the curing procedure. Ring specimens were compressed on a 72-cam device, whereas cylindrical rod and flat ones were tested on the "Instron"-device at the upper traverse speed 0.5 mm a minute. To preclude any unaxiality of loading and end squashing of cylindrical specimens, they were tested in special slides.

I. GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS (GFRP)

The delamination of specimens is known to be the result of failure of the matrix and the matrix-fibre interface. This accounts for the linear proportionality between the compression, σ_c , and shear, τ , strength [1,2] :

$$\sigma_c = A\tau \quad (1)$$

where A is experimental constant.

Figure I.

Shear and compression stress-strain plots of GFRP. I-ring specimens; different matrices (\bullet), changing the porosity (\blacktriangle) and the adhesive strength (\times). 2-dog-bone shaped specimens; different sizes (\blacktriangledown), the EDT-10 matrix. 3-dog-bone shaped specimens; different curing conditions of the EDT-10 matrix.

Ring specimens obey equation (I) regardless of the way τ is varied: by employing different matrices, changing the porosity or adhesion strength (Fig.I). Tests of rod specimens yield much higher strength values and a $\bar{\sigma}_c$ vs. τ relation quite different from that of equation (I). Following the reasoning in Ref.2, one can conclude that the failure of these specimens is brought about by the microbuckling of fibers rather than by the delamination. That composites may, in principle, fail according to this pattern has been demonstrated on model specimens reinforced with bars about 1 mm thick [3] as well as on GFRP specimens with fibres 130 μm in diameter [2]. Thus, we are aware of no other work where this mechanism would be described for specimens reinforced by commercial glass fibres 9-to-20 μm in diameter. To observe such failure behaviour, one has to suppress the delamination, which usually starts at lower stresses. In the present work, we have for the first time succeeded in surmounting this problem by manufacturing high-quality specimens of the geometry that precluded their squashing at the ends and unaxiality of loading by the grips in our testing assembly.

Figure 2.

The GFRP compression strength versus the volume fraction of fibres 19 μm in diameter. 1 - dog-bone shaped specimens with the EKT matrix; 2 - dog-bone shaped specimens with the EDT-10 matrix; 3 - ring specimens with the EDT-10 matrix.

Figure 2 gives the strength of rings and rods as functions of fibre volume content, V_f . The plots vary for different testing procedures and, consequently, different failure mechanisms. The strength of ring specimens grows with V_f much more steeply than that of rod specimens. The dashed lines correspond to the law of mixtures (Fig.2):

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m V_m \quad (2)$$

Here σ_f and σ_m are the fibre strength and matrix strength; V_f and V_m the respective volume contents.

The faster increase in the strength of rings than predicted by (2) can be ascribed to the fact that the GFRP shear strength shows some improvement at higher V_f [4]. As shown in Ref. [2], the influence of pores on the GFRP strength depends on the failure mechanism: the delamination-induced decrease in strength is much more pronounced in the presence of pores.

In Fig.3 the composite compression strength is plotted against the degree of Yarn twisting determined as a number of twists on a 1 m length (twisting degree). To reduce porosity, impregnation preceded the twisting of the yarn.

Figure 3.
The GFRP compression strength versus the thread twisting degree, the EDT-10 matrix. 1 - dog-bone shaped specimens; 2 - ring specimens; 3 - the misalignment angle of the outer fibres of

the yarn with linear density equal to 178 mg/m.

The fibres of twisted yarns cannot be strictly parallel to the specimen axis, but rather lie at a certain angle to it (Fig.3). Hence, compressive axial loading gives rise to transversal tensile stresses the value of which can be derived from the analogy with Ref. [5] :

$$\sigma_{\perp} = \sigma \langle \Psi \rangle = \frac{4}{3} \pi R N \sigma \quad (3)$$

Here $\langle \Psi \rangle$ is the mean angle between the axis of the specimen and that of the fibres, N is the yarn twisting degree, R is the yarn radius, and σ is the external load.

If it is presumed that the failure comes through delamination when the transversal strength of the composite is exceeded, one should expect these experimental relationships to become linear in the σ_0/σ_N - N coordinates and be described accordingly to [5] as:

$$\sigma_N = \sigma_0 / \left(1 + \frac{4\pi R N \sigma_0}{3\sigma_{1c}} \right) \quad (4)$$

where σ_0 and σ_N are the strengths of the composite with zero and "N" yarn twisting, respectively.

It can be shown that such linearization takes place, and the experimental points for both rings and rods (Fig.3) fall on the same straight line. This implies that starting from a certain degree of twisting (under 30 twists per meter) the rod specimens also fail through delamination. Equation (4) predicts not only the pattern but also the approximate value

of strength as a function of N . Experimental data support these predictions when σ_{IC} is equal to 200MPa which is slightly higher than the GFRP transversal strength. The composite strength being such a strong function of N suggests that even minute misalignment can have a very adverse effect on the composite compression strength. This may account for the considerable relative ease with which one can observe the GFRP failure through the fiber microbuckling when these fibres are thick (naturally, thick fibres are much more readily aligned than thin and flexible ones).

2. ORGANIC FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS (OFRP).

Since the elasticity modulus of aramide fibres is roughly one hundred times greater than that of the epoxide matrix, most of the loading is sustained by the fibres. The ultimate deformation under compression of aramide fibres (0.3-0.5%) is much lower than the deformation corresponding to the epoxide yield point (3-5%). The strength of OFRP is therefore limited by the load-carrying capacity of fibres at any feasible degree of reinforcement [6] :

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m V_m l_f / l_m \cong \sigma_f V_f \quad (5)$$

where e_f and e_m are the yield deformations of fibres and matrix, respectively.

The experimental dependence of the OFRP strength on the ratio of fibre and matrix volume fractions appears in Fig.4. Note that the dependence follows the rule of mixtures rather than eq. (5). It is also worth mentioning that the strength

of OFRP based on "amorphous" or "amorpho-crystalline" fibres makes little difference. The strength of these plastics is also rather insensitive to the testing procedure.

Figure 4.

The compression strength versus fibre volume fraction. I - OFRP fibres with amorphous (x) and amorpho-crystalline (o) structure, the cylindrical specimens (▼) amorphous fibres, flat specimens. 2 - plastic copper wires cylindrical specimens. 3 and 4 - the stress-strain plots for the OFRP volume fraction- 30 and 60% cylindrical specimens.

Extra polated to $V_f = 0$, this function gives $\bar{\sigma}_M = 85 \pm 10$ MPa which is in good agreement with the EDT-10 matrix yield point under tensile stress (80-90 MPa). At the other extreme, $V_f = 100\%$, one obtains $\bar{\sigma}_f = 400 \pm 40$ MPa. This value is considerably below the strength of organic fibres as measured by the loop bending test and the compression of the fibres fixed to the plate (700-900 MPa) [7,8]. These two tests suffer from important drawbacks. What the loop test produces is bending rather than uniform compression with the result that the fibre strength is likely to be overestimated. For example, the compression strength of an OFRP bar with the 50% (by volume) reinforcement degree as measured by bending is 500-800 MPa which is 2-3 times higher the real value. The compression of a fibre glued to the plate has another shortcoming for the

glue can restrict the development of plastic fibre deformation [9]. In this case, the resulting strength value is an overestimation, too.

Fig.4 also gives the compression strength versus V_f of composites manufactured out of the ETD-10 epoxy matrix and plastic copper fibres. Extrapolation of the obtained function to $V_f=100\%$ gives $\bar{\sigma}_f = 210\text{MPa}$ which agrees well with the yield point of copper wires 200-210MPa (at the 0.5-1.0% deformation). Unlike the aramide fibres which display plastic properties under compression only, a copper wire flows under tension as well thus making it possible to determine its yield strength which must be virtually the same for both compression and tension. From the analogy between the aramide and copper fibres, one can conclude the compression strength of organic fibres as equal to around 400MPa, rather than 700-800MPa

Figure 5.

The elasticity modulus (1) and the ultimate deformation (2) of OFRP with the EDT-10 matrix plotted against the volume fraction of amorphous aramide fibres.

It should be noted that the OFRP stress-strain plots are virtually linear right until the emergence of the developed shear line at around 45° to the fibre axis and the loss of the carrying capacity of the material. Increased fibre content reduces the composite yield strength (Fig.5). Hence, when the shear line appears, the critical stresses in the

fibres depend on the degree of reinforcement. This is in apparent contradiction with the rule of mixtures. A possible explanation may be that the polymer matrix restricts the development of the shear line in fibres and thus increases the the fibre yielding point [9]. This phenomenon has been observed in composites manufactured out of rigid matrices reinforced with plastic metallic fibres [10]. At elongations critical for the fibres, the epoxy resin is sufficiently elastic to drive up the yield point of the fibres in the composite. Note that this increment is determined by the carrying capacity of the matrix. One may ascribe this to the emergence of microzones of local plasticity in the elastic material, i.e. sites of plastic behaviour of the matrix and fibres. And the rule of mixtures naturally governs the conditions under which these zones become unstable.

We have also investigated the influence of stress concentrators on the OFRP compression strength (Fig.6). It should be pointed out that the development of a crack leads to a comparatively slight loss of strength.

Figure 6.

The ultimate deformation of amorphous fibre OFRP versus the notch length, C. Matrix modifier (DEG) content 10 (1), 30 v.%.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the failure behaviour of compressed GFRP depends on the manufacturing conditions and testing procedure. It should be noted that the strength of composites is differently affected by such variables as the degree of reinforcement and porosity. Consequently the failure mechanism has to be taken into consideration in discussing the influence of these factors on the compression strength of composites. Creating a new material, one must devise a testing procedure that would ensure the same failure mechanism as in the part manufactured out of this material.

For the OFRP the conclusion to be drawn from the study is that the strength dependence on the degree of reinforcement obeys the rule of mixtures and the strength of elementary fibres is 400 MPa. To enhance the compression strength of glass and organic fibre reinforced plastics, high-strength and rigid matrices should be used. This, however, is likely to reduce somewhat the tensile strength of the composites.

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